

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20747688

EVALUATION OF THE KINGDOM OF SAUDI ARABIA VISION 2030 IN PROVIDING ONLINE LEARNING PROGRAMS FOR STUDENTS WITH VISUAL IMPAIRMENTS TO IMPROVE ACCESSIBILITY FROM THEIR TEACHERS' PERSPECTIVE

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Received: 01/11/2025
Accepted: 26/12/2025

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ABSTRACT

This study evaluates the accessibility of online learning programs for students with visual impairments in the context of Saudi Arabia's Vision 2030, focusing on the perspectives of specialized educators. Employing a descriptive analytical approach, the research surveyed all 113 special education teachers from the Al-Noor Institute and the schools have programs for visual impairments in the Qassim region, utilizing a validated questionnaire that assessed both the current state of these programs and the barriers to effective implementation. The findings indicated that teachers perceived the contribution of online learning programs to accessibility as moderate (M=3.185, 64% relative weight), acknowledging their effectiveness in offering diverse information presentation methods and flexibility. However, significant challenges were identified, including students' limited skills in independently navigating these programs (M=3.212, 64% relative weight) and inadequate financial resources for assistive technologies. No significant differences in perceptions were found based on gender, educational qualifications, or years of experience. The study underscores the need for targeted training for both educators and students, increased investment in assistive technologies, and enhanced collaboration among stakeholders to align online learning solutions with Vision 2030 objectives for improving educational accessibility for visually impaired students.

KEYWORDS: Saudi Arabia Vision 2030, Online Learning Programs, Students With Visual Impairments, Accessibility, Teachers' Perspectives.

1. INTRODUCTION

The transformation of the education sector in Saudi Arabia is intricately linked to national aspirations for modernization and inclusion, as articulated in Vision 2030. Central to this transformation is the strategic integration of digital technologies into educational environments, aiming to ensure equitable access and enhance learning outcomes for all students, including those with disabilities (Karnas et al., 2023). Online learning platforms have become a cornerstone of educational reform, offering new opportunities for flexibility, accessibility, and individualized learning experiences (Almekawy & Alsolami, 2025).

For students with visual impairments, the promise of online learning is contingent upon the effective implementation of accessibility features and the thoughtful adaptation of digital content. These students frequently depend on assistive technologies such as screen readers, magnification tools, and alternative input methods to navigate online educational platforms and fully participate in digital classrooms (Alnajashi et al., 2023). However, the success of such programs is not solely defined by the availability of technology, but also by the degree to which educational systems, teachers, and institutional policies address the unique needs of these students (Obidat, 2022).

While Saudi Vision 2030 has set ambitious targets to create an inclusive, knowledge-based society, recent studies highlight persistent barriers to the realization of these goals for visually impaired students. These barriers include inconsistencies in the accessibility of e-learning platforms, insufficient professional training for teachers in the use of assistive technologies, and limited collaboration between educational authorities and technology providers (Alsolami, 2024). Teachers, as the primary facilitators of learning for visually impaired students, play a critical role in mediating access and fostering effective use of online learning tools. Their perspectives and expertise are essential for identifying practical obstacles and informing the development of more inclusive digital learning environments (Ghoneim et al., 2024).

Despite the centrality of the teacher's role, there is a noticeable gap in empirical research that systematically examines teachers' perspectives on the accessibility and effectiveness of online learning programs for visually impaired students within the context of Vision 2030. In particular, the experiences of teachers at Al-Noor Schools and the schools have programs for visual impairments in the Qassim region who work directly with visually impaired

students across elementary, middle, and secondary levels remain underexplored in the academic literature. In response to this gap, the present study aims to evaluate the effectiveness of online learning programs in improving accessibility for students with visual impairments, as perceived by their teachers in Al-Noor Schools and the schools have programs for visual impairments in Qassim region. This evaluation is situated within the broader goals of Vision 2030 and seeks to identify both the successes and the persistent challenges in the implementation of inclusive educational practices. By focusing on the lived experiences and professional insights of teachers, this research aspires to provide actionable recommendations for policymakers, educational leaders, and technology developers striving to create a more accessible and equitable educational system in Saudi Arabia.

2. PROBLEM STATEMENT

The Kingdom of Saudi Arabia's Vision 2030 has established ambitious goals for educational transformation, emphasizing digital innovation and inclusive learning environments that serve all students, including those with special needs (Alsolami, 2024). This national strategic framework recognizes the imperative of leveraging technological advancement to create equitable educational opportunities, particularly for students with visual impairments who have historically faced substantial barriers in accessing quality education (Belachew et al., 2025; Kumar & Kumar, 2024).

Contemporary research demonstrates that students with visual impairments encounter multifaceted challenges in traditional educational settings, necessitating specialized instructional approaches and adaptive technologies (Ghoneim et al., 2024; Guddad, 2025). Online learning platforms present significant potential for addressing these educational barriers through features such as assistive technologies, flexible content delivery, and personalized learning pathways (Oyekunle et al., 2024; Schauer et al., 2025). However, the successful implementation of these digital educational solutions depends critically on comprehensive teacher preparation, appropriate technological infrastructure, and systematic evaluation of program effectiveness (Escudeiro & Campos Gouveia, 2025; Sánchez et al., 2024).

Global statistics indicate that approximately 36 million individuals worldwide experience various degrees of visual impairment, with developing nations bearing a disproportionate burden of this demographic (United Nations, 2006). The World

Health Organization emphasizes the necessity for countries to ensure educational accessibility for individuals with visual impairments, enabling them to overcome barriers in educational participation and professional development (Gikandi et al., 2025). Within this international context, Saudi Arabia's commitment to inclusive education through Vision 2030 represents a significant opportunity to advance educational equity for students with visual impairments (Alnajashi et al., 2023).

Despite the theoretical advantages of online learning technologies, empirical evidence suggests that implementation effectiveness varies based on institutional capacity, teacher competency, and program design quality (Ahmad et al., 2024; Karnas et al., 2023). Research indicates that educators working with visually impaired students face distinct challenges in online learning environments, including limited access to specialized training, insufficient technical support, and inadequate assessment tools designed for diverse learning needs (Chabongwa, 2025; Obidat, 2022).

In the Qassim region of Saudi Arabia, Al-Noor schools and the schools have programs for visual impairments serve as primary educational institutions for students with visual impairments across elementary, intermediate, and secondary levels. Teachers within these institutions possess firsthand experience regarding the practical implementation of online learning programs and their effectiveness in meeting students' educational needs. However, limited research has systematically examined teachers' perspectives on how Vision 2030 initiatives have translated into tangible improvements in educational accessibility and quality for students with visual impairments. This knowledge gap represents a critical limitation in understanding the actual impact of national educational policies on specialized student populations. Without comprehensive evaluation of current practices, challenges, and outcomes from the perspective of frontline educators, policymakers lack essential information needed to refine and enhance online learning programs for students with visual impairments. Furthermore, the absence of systematic assessment undermines efforts to ensure that Vision 2030's inclusive education objectives are being effectively realized in practice. Therefore, this study addresses the urgent need to evaluate the implementation of Vision 2030's online learning initiatives for students with visual impairments through the lens of teacher experiences and perspectives in Al-Noor schools and the schools have programs for visual impairments within the Qassim

region. By examining both the achievements and limitations of current programs, this research aims to provide evidence-based insights that can inform policy development, improve educational practices, and advance the Kingdom's commitment to inclusive education for all students with visual impairments.

2.1. Research Questions

The problem of this study is clearly defined:

- What is the factual status of the contribution of online learning programs in improving accessibility for students with visual impairments, from their teachers' perspectives?
- What are the obstacles to providing online learning programs to improve accessibility for students with visual impairments, from their teachers' perspectives?
- Are there statistically significant differences in teachers' perceptions of the factual status of online learning programs in improving accessibility for visually impaired students, and the obstacles to providing them, attributable to variables (gender, educational qualification, years of experience)?

3. PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

This study aims to evaluate the effectiveness of Online learning programs in enhancing accessibility for students with visual impairments within the framework of Saudi Arabia's Vision 2030. By addressing key research questions, this investigation seeks to illuminate the status of online learning initiatives, and the challenges faced by educators in implementing these programs. Through a detailed analysis of teachers' perspectives, the study aspires to provide a nuanced understanding of the barriers and facilitators influencing the accessibility of education for visually impaired students. The findings of this research will be instrumental in identifying specific obstacles such as technological limitations, inadequate training, and insufficient institutional support that hinder the successful implementation of online learning programs. Furthermore, the study will explore the role of variables like gender, educational qualification, and teaching experience in shaping teachers' perceptions of these programs. By synthesizing these insights, this research aims to inform the development of tailored professional development initiatives and policy recommendations designed to enhance the delivery of online learning programs. This study seeks to contribute to the broader objective of creating an inclusive educational environment that meets the

diverse needs of students with visual impairments, aligning with the transformative goals set forth in Saudi Arabia's Vision 2030.

4. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

This study represents a pioneering effort to systematically investigate the perspectives of teachers regarding online learning programs for students with visual impairments in Saudi Arabia. The findings are expected to have significant practical implications, providing valuable insights for educational policymakers and stakeholders involved in the implementation of Vision 2030. By highlighting the status and obstacles faced in the delivery of online learning, this study can guide the formulation of effective strategies aimed at improving accessibility and educational outcomes for visually impaired students. The recommendations derived from this research will support the design of professional development programs that enhance teachers' competencies in utilizing online learning tools, fostering a more inclusive educational landscape.

5. LITERATURE REVIEW

The pursuit of educational equity for individuals with disabilities has gained momentum worldwide, anchored in international frameworks such as the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, which emphasizes the right to accessible information, communication, and educational opportunities for all (United Nations, 2006). Within this context, students with visual impairments represent a group whose access to quality education is uniquely dependent on the availability and effectiveness of specialized support, adaptive technologies, and inclusive pedagogical strategies (Chabongwa, 2025).

5.1. Online Learning and Students with Visual Impairments

Online learning platforms have become a pivotal element in contemporary education, providing alternative means for instructional delivery and enabling greater flexibility for diverse learners. For students with visual impairments, these platforms have the potential to bridge longstanding accessibility gaps by offering digital content in multiple formats, supporting screen readers, text-to-speech, and other assistive technologies (Escudeiro & Campos Gouveia, 2025). Many studies, such as those by Gikandi et al. (2025), Belachew et al. (2025), and Schauer et al. (2025), consistently demonstrate that, when properly designed and implemented, digital

learning environments can facilitate academic progress for learners with visual impairments, enabling them to achieve outcomes comparable to those of their sighted peers.

However, Guddad (2025) also reveals persistent challenges. The effectiveness of online learning programs for visually impaired students is intricately linked to the accessibility of educational resources, the technical skills of both students and teachers, and the institutional frameworks supporting inclusive practices. While technology can bridge geographical gaps and offer flexible learning modalities, its effectiveness hinges on the accessibility of online learning programs, content, and the preparedness of educators to utilize these tools effectively for students with VI (Oyekunle et al., 2024). The perspectives of teachers are crucial in understanding the on-the-ground realities of implementing accessible online learning, as they are at the forefront of delivering education and can provide valuable insights into the challenges and successes of such initiatives. Understanding these perspectives is vital for developing effective strategies and policies that align with the principles of inclusive education. Barriers such as limited teacher training in assistive technology, insufficient partnership between educational authorities and technology providers, and the lack of universally designed platforms continue to hinder full participation and achievement for this population (Ahmad et al., 2024).

5.2. An Overview of Educational Reforms for the Visually Impaired in Accordance with Saudi Vision 2030

The Kingdom of Saudi Arabia has articulated a transformative vision for its education sector through Vision 2030, which prioritizes digital transformation, inclusivity, and the development of human capital (Alsamiri et al., 2022). In alignment with this vision, Saudi Arabia has invested in a suite of digital learning initiatives, including the Madrasati platform, IEN National Education Portal, and various specialized resources to enhance access for students with disabilities (Alsamiri et al., 2022; Al-Asmari & Khan, 2014).

Historically, Saudi Arabia has taken significant steps to integrate students with visual impairments into mainstream education, beginning with the establishment of dedicated programs and expanding to the inclusion of accessibility features in national online learning programs (Al-Mousa, 2010). Nonetheless, the practical realization of these inclusivity aspirations remains an ongoing challenge. Research conducted in the Saudi context highlights

systemic issues such as variable platform accessibility, disparities in resource allocation, and the need for ongoing professional development for teachers working with students with visual impairments (Almekawy & Alsolami, 2024; Alsawalem, 2019).

5.3. Teachers' Views on Professional Practice

Teachers serve as critical mediators between educational policy and classroom practice, particularly in the realm of online learning for students with visual impairments. Their attitudes, training, and access to support resources directly impact both the quality and accessibility of learning experiences for their students (Ghoneim *et al.*, 2024). Multiple studies, such as Almekawy & Alsolami (2025); Ahmad *et al.* (2024); Ghoneim *et al.* (2024) indicate that teachers often perceive the use of e-learning platforms for visually impaired students as only moderately effective, citing barriers such as limited training opportunities, insufficient technical support, and an overall lack of collaboration with technology developers.

Moreover, the effectiveness of online learning is influenced by broader systemic considerations, including institutional commitment to universal design principles, ongoing evaluation of program accessibility, and the availability of specialized assistive technologies (Sánchez *et al.*, 2024). A recurring theme in the literature is the necessity of continuous professional development to equip teachers with the skills required to navigate and adapt digital learning environments for students with visual impairments (Kumar & Kumar, 2024).

Despite significant advancements in educational technology and policy, there remains a noticeable gap in empirical research that systematically investigates the perspectives of teachers regarding the accessibility and effectiveness of online learning programs for visually impaired students—particularly within the framework of Saudi Vision 2030. Studies focusing on the experiences of teachers at specialized institutions, such as Al-Noor Schools and the schools have programs for visual impairments in the Qassim region, are essential for identifying practical challenges, evaluating the real-world impact of policy initiatives, and informing future improvements in both technology and pedagogy. The literature underscores the potential of online learning to enhance accessibility and educational equity for students with visual impairments. However, the realization of this potential is contingent upon the integration of universal design, institutional support, ongoing

teacher training, and sustained collaboration among stakeholders. Evaluating these dimensions from the perspective of teachers—who are at the forefront of implementation—offers invaluable insight for advancing inclusive education in Saudi Arabia and achieving the objectives set forth by Vision 2030.

6. STUDY METHODOLOGY

The descriptive analytical approach was utilized in this study, as it aligns with the nature of the subject. This approach involves examining the experiences, perceptions, and challenges faced by teachers regarding the provision of online learning programs for students with visual impairments within the context of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia's Vision 2030, with a specific focus on improving accessibility. The study specifically investigates how variables such as gender, years of experience, educational qualifications, and academic specialization of the participating teachers influence their perspectives. This approach facilitates the direct collection of data from the target population (teachers), aiming to comprehensively diagnose various specific aspects of the online learning programs' implementation and accessibility for visually impaired students under Vision 2030, without being confined to a single influencing factor.

6.1. The Study Community

The study community includes all male and female teachers of visually impaired students in Al-Noor schools and the schools have programs for visual impairments at the primary, intermediate, and secondary levels in the Qassim region, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, totaling (113) teachers, according to the statistics of the Special Education Department in Qassim for the academic year 2024 / 2025.

6.2. The Study Sample

A comprehensive survey method was adopted for the study, encompassing all individuals in the study community. The sample consisted of all teachers mentioned in the study community, with a total number of (113) male and female teachers, as shown in Table (1). Among the participants, 53.1% (60) were male, while 46.9% (53) were female. Regarding educational qualifications, most participants held a bachelor's degree, representing 60.2% (68) of the sample, followed by those with a master's degree at 30.1% (34), while those holding a doctorate degree constituted 9.7% (11) of the total sample. As for years of experience, 20.4% (23) of the participants had less than 5 years of experience, 35.4% (40) had between 5 and 10 years of experience, while 24.8% (28) had

between 11 and 15 years of experience, and 19.5% (22) had more than 15 years of experience.

Table (1): Characteristics of the Study Sample.

Variable	Categories	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	60	53.1%
	Female	53	46.9%
Educational Qualification	Bachelor's Degree	68	60.2%
	Master's Degree	34	30.1%
	Doctorate	11	9.7%
Experience	Less than 5 years	23	20.4%
	5 - 10 years	40	35.4%
	11 - 15 years	28	24.8%
	More than 15 years	22	19.5%

Table (1) presents the demographic profile of the 113 participating teachers, revealing a near-balanced gender ratio, predominance of bachelor's degree holders, and a broad distribution of teaching experience among educators of visually impaired students. The sample exhibited a relatively balanced gender distribution and was predominantly composed of teachers holding a bachelor's degree (60.2%). Professional experience was moderately distributed, with the largest proportion (35.4%) having 5-10 years of experience and a notable segment (19.5%) possessing more than 15 years, reflecting a mix of early-career, mid-career, and highly experienced educators specialized in teaching visually impaired students.

6.3. Study Tool

Data was collected through a questionnaire designed to explore the factual status of the contribution of online learning programs in improving accessibility for students with visual impairments, as well as the obstacles hindering this, from their teachers' perspectives. This questionnaire was developed based on previous studies related to online learning and accessibility for visually impaired students, such as the study of Amponsah & Bekele (2023) and the study of Baruah (2018). The questionnaire is divided into two main sections: The first section is dedicated to collecting demographic information about the participants, including gender, educational qualifications, and years of academic experience. The second section focuses on evaluating the main aspects of online learning programs' contribution to improving accessibility for visually impaired students and the obstacles faced. It is further divided into two areas: Area One: The factual status of online learning programs in improving accessibility for students with visual impairments, from their teachers' perspectives. This area includes (30) items and aims to evaluate the reality of online learning programs in enhancing accessibility for visually impaired students from their teachers'

perspectives, covering aspects such as the availability of support, training, and flexible program design. Area Two: Obstacles to providing online learning programs to improve accessibility for students with visual impairments, from their teachers' perspectives. This area includes (14) statements, encompassing potential obstacles that hinder this accessibility, such as weak training and resources, lack of awareness, and increased workload, in addition to challenges related to students, parents, and partnerships. Overall, the questionnaire aims to provide a comprehensive evaluation of the role of online learning programs in improving accessibility, while highlighting the most prominent challenges.

6.4. Validity and Reliability

To ensure the validity of the questionnaire in measuring the intended constructs, the initial version was reviewed by ten experts specialized in special education and online learning for visually impaired individuals. These experts evaluated the items for their relevance to the constructs being measured and the accuracy of their formulation and provided necessary feedback and recommendations for modification. Items that did not achieve an agreement rate of at least 80% were revised or removed.

The questionnaire was piloted with a sample of (30) male and female teachers of visually impaired students, who were excluded from the main study sample. The internal consistency of the tool was assessed using Pearson correlation coefficients, which measured the correlation between each item and the total score for its respective dimension. The correlation coefficients for Area One "The factual status of the contribution of online learning programs in improving accessibility" ranged from 0.741 to 0.862, while for Area Two "Obstacles to providing online learning programs to improve accessibility" ranged from 0.837 to 0.893, indicating high internal consistency of the items in the questionnaire.

For reliability, the researcher used split-half reliability and Cronbach's alpha. The split-half reliability coefficients ranged from 0.827 to 0.903, while Cronbach's alpha coefficients ranged from 0.803 to 0.892, reflecting good reliability in measuring the intended constructs of the questionnaire.

6.5. Statistical Methods

The researcher used the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS v. 28) to analyze the study data. Descriptive statistics including means, standard deviations, and relative weights were used. Additionally, independent samples t-test was employed to detect differences according to the gender variable, and one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to detect differences according

to educational qualification and years of experience variables.

6.6. Presentation of the Results Related to the First Question

To answer the first research question, which is: "What is the factual status of the contribution of online learning programs in improving accessibility for students with visual impairments, from their teachers' perspectives?", the researcher calculated the means, standard deviations, and relative weights for the responses of teachers of visually impaired students to the questionnaire items concerning "The factual status of the contribution of online learning programs in improving accessibility." The following table illustrates these results.

Table (2): Mean, Standard Deviation, And Relative Weight Results for the Questionnaire Items on the Factual Status of the Contribution of Online Learning Programs in Improving Accessibility for Students with Visual Impairments, From Their Teachers' Perspectives.

No.	Items	Mean	Std. Deviation	Relative Weight	Level	Ranking
9	Online learning programs offer multiple and accessible ways to present information (e.g., text-to-speech, screen reader compatibility) for students with visual impairments.	4.575	0.497	92%	Very High	1
24	The flexibility in time and place offered by online learning programs significantly enhances learning accessibility for students with visual impairments.	4.531	0.501	91%	Very High	2
14	Assessment methods within online learning programs are designed to be accessible and fairly evaluate the performance of students with visual impairments.	4.522	0.502	90%	Very High	3
19	Online learning programs contribute to making education more accessible for students with visual impairments by reducing time, effort, and travel-related barriers.	4.478	0.502	90%	Very High	4
29	Online learning programs effectively implement principles of Universal Design for Learning (UDL) to ensure accessibility for students with visual impairments.	4.469	0.501	89%	Very High	5
4	Online learning programs used are inherently designed with accessibility features suitable for students with visual impairments.	4.460	0.501	89%	Very High	6
11	Online learning programs provide accessible communication channels between students with visual impairments and their teachers.	3.602	0.492	72%	High	7
6	Instructions and navigation within online learning programs are clear and accessible for students with visual impairments.	3.540	0.501	71%	High	8
13	Online learning programs allow teachers to provide feedback to students with visual impairments in accessible formats.	3.522	1.166	70%	High	9
23	Academic content delivered through online learning programs can be made fully accessible to students with visual impairments with reasonable effort.	3.522	1.061	70%	High	10
21	Online learning programs inherently support differentiation by allowing content to be presented in multiple accessible formats, catering to individual differences among students with visual impairments.	3.478	0.502	70%	High	11

*EVALUATION OF THE KINGDOM OF SAUDI ARABIA VISION 2030 IN PROVIDING ONLINE
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18	Online learning programs make it easier for students with visual impairments to access, download, and manage educational content in various accessible formats.	3.460	1.053	69%	High	12
16	Online learning programs enhance my ability to communicate effectively and accessibly with my students with visual impairments.	3.434	0.498	69%	High	13
26	I can easily adapt or modify materials within online learning programs to ensure they are accessible for my students with visual impairments.	3.434	0.498	69%	High	14
28	Online learning programs can easily integrate with specialized online resources and assistive technology tools to enhance accessibility for students with visual impairments.	3.425	1.092	68%	High	15
8	Online learning programs facilitate the participation of students with visual impairments in practical and non-classroom activities through accessible means.	3.407	1.032	68%	High	16
1	The Ministry of Education provides clear guidelines for ensuring accessibility in online learning programs for students with visual impairments.	3.407	0.493	68%	High	17
3	Sufficient technical support is available to help teachers ensure online learning programs are accessible for students with visual impairments.	3.389	1.073	68%	Medium	18
7	Online learning programs effectively contribute to achieving learning goals for students with visual impairments by enhancing their access to educational content.	3.080	1.396	62%	Medium	19
17	Online learning programs offer accessible means for teachers to communicate with the parents of students with visual impairments regarding their progress and accessibility needs.	2.991	1.467	60%	Medium	20
27	Online learning platforms facilitate the exchange of best practices among teachers regarding how to improve accessibility for students with visual impairments.	2.974	1.485	59%	Medium	21
12	Online learning programs enable students with visual impairments to engage in individual and group research projects through accessible tools and platforms.	2.974	1.398	59%	Medium	22
22	The ability to record and review lessons within online learning programs improves learning accessibility and retention for students with visual impairments.	2.876	1.440	58%	Medium	23
2	I have received adequate training on how to make online learning programs accessible for students with visual impairments.	2.867	1.346	57%	Medium	24
5	Students with visual impairments are provided with the necessary assistive technologies to effectively access online learning programs.	1.602	0.492	32%	Very Low	25
10	Online learning programs significantly improve access to a wider range of learning resources and references for students with visual impairments.	1.584	0.495	32%	Very Low	26
30	Students with visual impairments can effectively apply the knowledge and skills gained through accessible online learning programs in various contexts.	1.540	0.501	31%	Very Low	27
20	Online learning programs are flexible enough to accommodate the individual learning paces and accessibility needs of students with visual impairments.	1.522	0.502	30%	Very Low	28
15	Online learning programs contribute to creating an inclusive and engaging learning environment for students with visual impairments by offering diverse and accessible interactive elements.	1.478	0.502	30%	Very Low	29
25	Improved accessibility through online learning programs positively impacts the motivation of students with visual impairments to learn.	1.407	0.493	28%	Very Low	30
	Overall mean value	3.185	0.178	64%	Medium	

As shown in Table (2), teachers' perceptions of the actual contribution of online learning programs to

improving accessibility for students with visual impairments yielded an overall mean of 3.185 (SD =

0.178), corresponding to a relative weight of 64% and interpreted as medium. Item-level analysis revealed considerable heterogeneity in perceived effectiveness.

The highest agreement was observed for items related to the inherent technical affordances of the programs. Teachers overwhelmingly recognized that online learning platforms provide multiple accessible modalities for content delivery ($M = 4.575$, 92%) and offer significant flexibility in time and place ($M = 4.531$, 91%), followed closely by accessible assessment practices ($M = 4.522$, 90%). These results suggest that teachers view the foundational accessibility infrastructure, particularly screen-reader compatibility, text-to-speech functionality, and reduction of physical barriers, as the strongest current contribution of online learning programs.

In contrast, the lowest-rated items clustered around student engagement, motivation, and pedagogical personalization. Teachers reported very low effectiveness in enhancing student motivation ($M = 1.407$, 28%), creating inclusive and interactive learning environments ($M = 1.478$, 30%), and accommodating individual learning paces ($M = 1.522$, 30%). Similarly, limited provision of assistive technologies (item 5: $M = 1.602$, 32%) and inadequate

teacher training (item 2: $M = 2.867$, 57%) further underscore systemic implementation deficits. This marked divergence between high ratings for technical features and very low ratings for motivational and interactive outcomes indicates that, while online learning programs possess robust accessibility tools in principle, their real-world application remains largely teacher-dependent and fails to translate into meaningful engagement or inclusive pedagogy for visually impaired students.

6.7. Presentation of the Results Related to the Second Question

To answer the second research question, which is: "What are the obstacles to providing online learning programs to improve accessibility for students with visual impairments, from their teachers' perspectives?", the researcher calculated the means, standard deviations, and relative weights for the responses of teachers of visually impaired students to the questionnaire items concerning "Obstacles to providing online learning programs to improve accessibility." The following table illustrates these results.

Table (3): Mean, Standard Deviation, and Relative Weight Results for the Questionnaire Items on Obstacles to Providing Online Learning Programs to Improve Accessibility for Students with Visual Impairments, From Their Teachers' Perspectives.

No.	Items	Mean	Std. Deviation	Relative Weight	Level	Rank
1	Poor training of teachers of students with VI on providing online learning programs and ensuring their accessibility.	1.920	0.803	38%	Low	10
2	The school's limited financial resources to provide necessary equipment, software, and assistive technologies for effective and accessible online learning programs.	3.142	0.854	63%	Medium	2
3	Weakness of teaching culture in utilizing online learning programs to improve accessibility among teachers of students with VI.	1.540	0.501	31%	Very Low	13
4	The teacher lack of awareness of the importance or methods of adapting online learning programs to improve accessibility for students with visual impairments.	2.265	1.069	45%	Low	8
5	Poor awareness among students with visual impairments of the benefits and functionalities of online learning programs designed to be accessible.	1.885	0.853	38%	Low	12
6	Increased workload and multiplicity of tasks for teachers of students with VI when implementing and adapting online learning programs for accessibility.	2.487	1.103	50%	Low	6
7	The reluctance of students with VI to engage with online learning programs, potentially due to previous negative experiences or accessibility challenges.	2.938	0.805	59%	Medium	4
8	The poor skills of students with VI in independently navigating and utilizing various online learning programs and their accessibility features.	3.212	1.454	64%	Medium	1
9	Difficulty in tailoring online learning programs and materials to meet the diverse individual accessibility needs and learning styles of students with VI.	1.903	0.767	38%	Low	11

10	Lack of parental engagement or support in assisting students with VI with their online learning programs and related accessibility requirements at home.	3.000	0.824	60%	Medium	3
11	The poor technological literacy or culture among parents of students with VI, hindering their ability to support accessible online learning.	1.513	0.502	30%	Very Low	14
12	Lack of readily available online learning programs and platforms that are inherently designed with comprehensive accessibility features for students with visual impairments.	2.319	1.120	46%	Low	7
13	Insufficient professional development and continuous support for special education teachers on the latest technological innovations and best practices for accessible online learning.	2.053	0.822	41%	Low	9
14	Weak partnership and collaboration between the Ministry of Education, technology developers, and accessibility experts in creating and implementing effective and accessible online learning solutions for students with visual impairments.	2.726	1.054	55%	Medium	5
Overall mean value		2.350	0.248	47%	Low	

Table (3)presents teachers' perceptions of the obstacles hindering the effective implementation of accessible online learning programs for students with visual impairments. The overall mean of 2.350 (SD = 0.248), equivalent to a relative weight of 47%, reflects a generally low level of perceived obstruction. However, substantial variation exists across individual barriers.

The highest-rated obstacles centered on student competency and institutional resource constraints. Teachers identified students' poor independent navigation and technical skills with online platforms and accessibility features as the primary barrier (M = 3.212, 64%), closely followed by limited school budgets for procuring essential hardware, software, and assistive technologies (M = 3.142, 63%). Lack of parental involvement at home (M = 3.000, 60%) and students' reluctance to engage (M = 2.938, 59%) further emerged as notable medium-level impediments, collectively pointing to a triad of student skill deficits, financial limitations, and insufficient home support as the most pressing challenges.

Conversely, items receiving the lowest ratings suggest that certain commonly assumed barriers are less salient in the present context. Teachers assigned very low importance to poor parental technological literacy (M = 1.513, 30%) and an underdeveloped professional culture among educators regarding accessibility (M = 1.540, 31%). These findings imply that attitudinal or cultural resistance among teachers and parents is not a dominant obstacle; rather, the critical bottlenecks lie in tangible resource availability, student digital proficiency, and systemic coordination between educational authorities and technology providers.

Taken together, the pattern of responses indicates that, although the overall obstacle level is low to moderate, targeted interventions addressing student

training, institutional funding, and strengthened home-school partnerships are likely to yield the greatest improvements in the accessibility and effectiveness of online learning programs for visually impaired learners in Saudi Arabia.

6.8. Presentation Of the Results Related to the Third Question

To answer the third research question, which is: "Are there statistically significant differences at the significance level ($\alpha=0.05$) in teachers' perceptions of the factual status of online learning programs in improving accessibility for visually impaired students, and the obstacles to providing them, attributable to variables (gender, educational qualification, years of experience)?", Prior to conducting the statistical analyses, the researcher checked the normality of data distribution for the questionnaire dimensions, and found that it follows a normal distribution, which allowed for the use of parametric statistical methods.

Accordingly, the Independent Samples T-Test was applied to analyze the differences according to the gender variable, and the One-Way ANOVA test was applied to analyze the differences according to the educational qualification and years of experience variables. The results of this analysis are presented below:

Firstly: Differences According to Gender Variable

To determine the differences in teachers' perceptions of the factual status of online learning programs in improving accessibility for visually impaired students, and the obstacles to providing them, attributable to the gender variable, parametric statistical methods were used, specifically the Independent Samples T-Test, to analyze the differences between the responses of male and

female teachers. Table (4) presents the results of this test.

Table (4): Independent Samples T-Test Results for Teachers' Perceptions of the Factual Status of Online Learning Programs in Improving Accessibility for Visually Impaired Students, And the Obstacles to Providing Them, According to Gender Variable (Male, Female).

Dimension	Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t-value	Sig.	(η ²)	95% CI	
								Lower	Upper
Online Learning Programs Contribution Status	Male	60	3.178	0.167	-0.455	0.650	0.002	-0.082	0.051
	Female	53	3.193	0.19					
Online Learning Programs Provision Challenges	Male	60	2.364	0.253	0.642	0.522	0.004	-0.063	0.123
	Female	53	2.334	0.243					

Table (4) shows no statistically significant gender differences in teachers' perceptions of either the current contribution of online learning programs to accessibility ($t(111) = -0.455, p = .650, \eta^2 = .002$) or the obstacles to their effective implementation ($t(111) = 0.642, p = .522, \eta^2 = .004$). Effect sizes were negligible, indicating virtually identical views between male and female teachers.

An independent-samples t-test was conducted to determine whether teachers' perceptions of (a) the factual contribution of online learning programs to accessibility and (b) the obstacles to their provision differed significantly by gender.

Results, presented in Table 4, revealed no statistically significant differences on either dimension. Male and female teachers rated the contribution of online learning programs almost identically (males: $M = 3.178, SD = 0.167$; females: $M = 3.193, SD = 0.190$), $t(111) = -0.455, p = .650, \eta^2 = .002$. Perceptions of implementation obstacles followed the same pattern (males: $M = 2.364, SD = 0.253$; females: $M = 2.334, SD = 0.243$), $t(111) = 0.642, p = .522, \eta^2 = .004$. The extremely small effect sizes and confidence intervals containing zero confirm that these minor numerical differences are statistically meaningless.

This absence of gender-based variation is noteworthy. It demonstrates a high degree of consensus between male and female educators

regarding both the strengths and the limitations of current online learning programs for visually impaired students.

Such consistency has clear practical implications. It indicates that gender does not moderate teachers' evaluations in this domain and therefore strengthens the generalizability of the study's overall findings across the teaching workforce.

Accordingly, future training programs, technical support initiatives, and policy recommendations can be designed and implemented uniformly without the need for gender-specific adaptations, ensuring equitable and efficient resource allocation in the pursuit of inclusive education under Saudi Vision 2030.

Secondly: Differences To Educational Qualification

To analyze the differences in teachers' perceptions of the factual status of online learning programs in improving accessibility for visually impaired students, and the obstacles to providing them, according to the educational qualification variable.

The One-Way ANOVA test was used to analyze the differences between educational qualification categories (bachelor's degree, master's degree, Doctorate). Table (5) presents the results of this analysis:

Table (5): One-Way ANOVA Results for Teachers' Perceptions of the Factual Status of Online Learning Programs in Improving Accessibility for Visually Impaired Students, And the Obstacles to Providing Them, According to Educational Qualification Variable.

Dimension	Source	SS	Df	MS	F	Sig.	η ²
Online Learning Programs: Contribution Status	Between Groups	0.015	2	0.007	0.228	0.8	0.004
	Within Groups	3.523	110	0.032			
	Total	3.538	112				
Online Learning Programs: Provision Challenges	Between Groups	0.063	2	0.031	0.505	0.61	0.009
	Within Groups	6.804	110	0.062			
	Total	6.867	112				

Table (5) reveals no statistically significant differences in teachers' perceptions of either the contribution of online learning programs ($F(2, 110) = 0.228, p = .800, \eta^2 = .004$) or implementation obstacles

($F(2, 110) = 0.505, p = .610, \eta^2 = .009$) across educational qualification levels (Bachelor's, Master's, Doctorate). Effect sizes were negligible, indicating

highly consistent perceptions regardless of formal academic preparation.

A one-way between-subjects ANOVA was conducted to examine whether teachers' perceptions of the two core dimensions varied according to their highest educational qualification (Bachelor's, Master's, or Doctorate).

The analysis revealed no statistically significant differences on either dimension. Teachers' evaluations of the factual contribution of online learning programs to accessibility remained virtually identical across qualification levels, $F(2, 110) = 0.228$, $p = .800$, $\eta^2 = .004$. A parallel pattern emerged for perceived obstacles to implementation, $F(2, 110) = 0.505$, $p = .610$, $\eta^2 = .009$.

With effect sizes close to zero, these results clearly indicate that formal academic preparation exerts no discernible influence on how teachers assess either the strengths or the barriers of accessible online learning programs.

This striking uniformity carries important implications. It suggests that the observed perceptions are shaped primarily by shared professional experiences and systemic conditions

within the field of visual impairment education rather than by differences in advanced academic training.

Consequently, the consistency of views across Bachelor's, Master's, and Doctorate holders strengthens confidence in the robustness and generalizability of the study's overall findings within this specialized teaching population. It also implies that future professional development initiatives can be designed and delivered uniformly, without the need to tailor content differently for teachers holding higher degrees.

Thirdly: Variable Differences in Years of Experience

To analyze the differences in teachers' perceptions of the factual status of online learning programs in improving accessibility for visually impaired students, and the obstacles to providing them, according to the years of experience variable.

The One-Way ANOVA test was used to analyze the differences between years of experience categories. Table (6) presents the results of this analysis:

Table (6): One-Way ANOVA Results for Teachers' Perceptions of the Factual Status of Online Learning Programs in Improving Accessibility for Visually Impaired Students, And the Obstacles to Providing Them, According to Years of Experience Variable.

Dimension	Source	SS	df	MS	F	Sig.	η^2
Online Learning Programs: Contribution Status	Between Groups	0.067	3	0.022	0.701	0.55	0.019
	Within Groups	3.471	109	0.032			
	Total	3.538	112				
Online Learning Programs: Provision Challenges	Between Groups	0.327	3	0.109	1.815	0.15	0.048
	Within Groups	6.54	109	0.06			
	Total	6.867	112				

Table (6) demonstrates no statistically significant differences in teachers' perceptions of either the contribution of online learning programs to accessibility ($F(3, 109) = 0.701$, $p = .550$, $\eta^2 = .019$) or the obstacles to implementation ($F(3, 109) = 1.815$, $p = .150$, $\eta^2 = .048$) across the four experience categories. The small effect sizes confirm that years of teaching experience exert no substantive influence on respondents' evaluations.

A one-way between-subjects ANOVA was conducted to determine whether years of professional experience (<5 years, 5–10 years, 11–15 years, and >15 years) influenced teachers' perceptions of the two main dimensions.

Results revealed no statistically significant differences on either dimension. Specifically, teachers' views of the factual contribution of online learning programs to accessibility remained consistent across experience levels, $F(3, 109) = 0.701$,

$p = .550$, $\eta^2 = .019$. A similar pattern emerged for perceived obstacles, $F(3, 109) = 1.815$, $p = .150$, $\eta^2 = .048$.

Given that both effect sizes were small and explained less than 5% of the variance, years of experience appear to play a negligible role in shaping these perceptions.

This consistency is noteworthy. It indicates a remarkable consensus among early-career, mid-career, and veteran educators regarding both the strengths and limitations of current online learning programs for visually impaired students. Such uniformity strongly suggests that the identified challenges are systemic in nature rather than tied to individual professional maturity or accumulated classroom exposure.

Consequently, interventions aimed at enhancing teacher training, boosting student digital literacy, and upgrading technical infrastructure are likely to

be equally relevant and well-received across all experience levels, with minimal risk of differential uptake or resistance.

7. LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

Although the present study provides valuable insights, several limitations should be acknowledged when interpreting the findings. First, the sample was drawn exclusively from teachers working in Al-Noor Schools and other institutions with dedicated visual-impairment programs in the Qassim region. Consequently, the results may not fully reflect the experiences, resources, or implementation contexts found in other regions of Saudi Arabia, particularly urban centers such as Riyadh or Jeddah, or more rural and remote governorates where infrastructure and technical support may differ substantially. This geographic and institutional specificity limits the generalizability of the findings to the national level.

Second, despite efforts to include the entire accessible population, a small proportion of eligible teachers either declined to participate or returned incomplete questionnaires. Although the final sample of 113 respondents represented a census of those who consented, this non-response may have introduced minor self-selection bias.

Third, reliance on a primarily quantitative survey, supplemented by limited qualitative input, restricted the depth of exploration into teachers' lived experiences and contextual nuances. Future studies employing in-depth interviews, focus groups, or classroom observations could yield richer insights into day-to-day challenges and coping strategies.

Finally, the cross-sectional design captures perceptions at a single point in time and cannot establish causality or track changes in attitudes and practices as online learning programs continue to evolve under Vision 2030 initiatives.

Addressing these limitations in future research through broader geographic sampling, higher response rates, longitudinal designs, and multi-method approaches would strengthen the evidence base and enhance the applicability of findings across the Kingdom.

8. CONCLUSION

This study offers valuable insights into teachers' perceptions of the effectiveness of online learning programs in improving educational accessibility for visually impaired students in Saudi Arabia, within the broader framework of Vision 2030. The results indicate that, although teachers recognize the considerable potential of online learning programs, their implementation remains inconsistent and falls

short of expectations. Teachers particularly valued the availability of multiple accessible formats within these programs; however, they consistently highlighted substantial challenges related to student motivation and engagement. Key barriers to successful implementation include inadequate training for both teachers and students, insufficient technical support, and limited access to appropriate digital resources. Notably, the perceived need for improvement in these areas was consistent across demographic variables, including gender, educational qualifications, and years of teaching experience.

These findings underscore the urgent need for targeted professional development initiatives and robust systemic support to optimize the delivery and impact of online learning programs for visually impaired learners. By systematically addressing the identified barriers, educators and policymakers can more effectively harness online learning programs to foster inclusive, engaging, and accessible educational environments that align with the ambitions of Saudi Vision 2030.

8.1. Recommendations And Future Directions

Based on the teachers' perspectives elicited in this study, the following evidence-based recommendations are proposed to enhance the effectiveness of online learning programs for visually impaired students in the context of Saudi Arabia's Vision 2030:

- **Professional Development for Teachers:** Design and deliver ongoing, specialized training programs focusing on the pedagogical and technical aspects of online learning programs, with particular emphasis on the integration of assistive technologies tailored to the needs of visually impaired students.
- **Strengthened Technical Support Infrastructure:** Establish dedicated, responsive technical support teams capable of providing timely assistance to both teachers and students, thereby maximizing the educational potential of online learning programs.
- **Collaboration with Stakeholders:** Promote strategic partnerships among the Ministry of Education, educational technology providers, and higher education institutions to ensure that online learning programs are developed and continuously updated with accessibility as a core design principle.
- **Continuous Evaluation and Feedback:** Institute regular, structured evaluation

processes that incorporate feedback from teachers, students, and other stakeholders to iteratively refine online learning programs and improve their accessibility, usability, and engagement levels.

- **Future Research Directions:** Encourage future research to explore the perspectives of various

stakeholders, including students and parents, using diverse methodologies, such as interviews and case studies, to gain a deeper understanding of the challenges and opportunities associated with online learning programs for students with visual impairments.

Acknowledgement: The researcher expresses gratitude to all the teachers who work with students with visual impairments in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, including educators from specialized institutes, mainstream schools with inclusion programs, and Online learning centers, for their valuable cooperation and participation in this study. Special appreciation is extended to the teachers who shared their experiences and perspectives regarding the implementation of Vision 2030's online learning initiatives for visually impaired students.

Compliance with Ethical Standards: This research was conducted in accordance with ethical standards for academic research involving human participants. All participants were informed about the nature and purpose of the study, and their consent was obtained prior to data collection. The confidentiality and anonymity of all participants were maintained throughout the research process. The study adhered to the ethical guidelines established by relevant academic institutions and research bodies in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia.

Conflict of Interest: The author declares that there are no potential conflicts of interest related to the research, authorship, or publication of this study. This research was conducted independently without any financial or personal relationships that could inappropriately influence the work or conclusions presented herein.

REFERENCES

- Ahmad, N., Anak Nugak, M., Abd Rahman, S. F., & Razak, N. (2024). Exploring challenges and impacts: Insights from school teachers in virtual learning environments. *Arab World English Journal*, (10), 172-190. <https://doi.org/10.24093/awej/call10.12>
- Almekawy, I. K., & Alsolami, A. S. (2025). The Use of E-learning Platforms in Teaching Students with Visual Impairments from their Teachers' Perspective. *Journal of Education-Sohag University*, 129(129). https://edusohag.journals.ekb.eg/article_407536_159f3014c3b196b95bce5e5b4388afef.pdf
- Alnajashi, A., Alnajashi, S., & Alnajashi, A. (2023). "I Like to Be Independent": Experience of Visually Disabled Students with Online Learning in Saudi Arabia. *Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology-TOJET*, 22(4), 1-10. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1409826>
- Alsolami, A. (2024). The Educational Journey of Students with Disabilities in Saudi Arabia: From Isolation to Inclusive Education. *Remedial and Special Education*, 45(6), 359-368. <https://doi.org/10.1177/07419325241240058>
- Amponsah, S., & Bekele, T. A. (2023). Exploring strategies for including visually impaired students in online learning. *Education and Information Technologies*, 28(8), 9355-9377. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-022-11145-x>
- Baruah, T. D. (2018). E-learning as a medium for facilitating learners' support services under open and distance learning: An evaluative study. *Technology for Efficient Learner Support Services in Distance Education*, 93-112. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-13-2300-3_5
- Belachew, M., Adamu, A., Ashete, A., & Mengistie, S. (2025). The impact of digital empowerment training on the awareness of assistive technologies and digital competence skills among students with visual impairment. *Disability and Rehabilitation: Assistive Technology*, 1-13. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17483107.2025.2508395>
- Biswalo, P. L. (2024). Assistive technologies for the visually impaired learners: Are teachers adequately trained to use assistive technologies? *Signals and Communication Technology*, 163-179. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-57880-9_8
- Chabongwa, K. (2025). *Challenges faced in teaching science to pupils with visual impairment: a case study of Phatlogo primary school in Francistown, Botswana* (Doctoral dissertation). <https://dspace.unza.zm/handle/123456789/9200>
- Escudeiro, P., & Campos Gouveia, M. (2025). Leveraging MOOCs for individuals with visual

- impairments. *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, 354-360. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-93864-1_23
- Ghoneim, R., Aljedaani, W., Bryce, R., Javed, Y., & Khan, Z. I. (2024). Why are other teachers more inclusive in online learning than us? Exploring challenges faced by teachers of blind and visually impaired students: A literature review. *Computers*, 13(10), 247. <https://doi.org/10.3390/computers13100247>
- Gikandi, J., Kimaru, S., Mwangi, J., & Mugwe, M. (2025). Assessment of the benefits and challenges of digital braille assistive devices in promoting inclusivity of learners with visual impairment in Kenya. *Acitya: Journal of Teaching and Education*, 7(2), 285-316. <https://doi.org/10.30650/ajte.v7i2.4482>
- Gill, K., Sharma, R., & Gupta, R. (2017). Empowering visually disabled students through E-learning at higher education: problems and solutions. *IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 22(8), 27-35. <https://doi.org/10.9790/0837-2208072735>
- Guddad, P. (2025). Challenges faced by the visually impaired students during online learning: Lessons for teachers. *Dibon Journal of Education*, 1(1), 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.64169/dje.6>
- Karnas, M., Alpaydın, B., & Eker, A. (2023). Implications of distance education on children with disabilities. *Support for Learning*, 38(2), 98-118. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-9604.12437>
- Kumar, P., & Kumar, S. (2024). Digital Horizons in Special Education: Pioneering Transformational Technologies for Individuals with Visual Impairments. *Educating for Societal Transitions*, 64. <https://books.google.com.eg/books?hl=en&lr=&id=XAgJEQAAQBAJ&oi=fnd&pg=PA64>
- Obidat, A. H. (2022). Bibliometric analysis of global scientific literature on the accessibility of an integrated E-Learning model for students with disabilities. *Contemporary Educational Technology*, 14(3), ep374. <https://doi.org/10.30935/cedtech/12064>
- Oyekunle, R. A., Chukwura, H. C., Talpur, N., & Balogun, A. O. (2024). Development of an Inclusive E-Learning Platform for Visually Impaired Students. *Studies in Learning and Teaching*, 5(3), 815-851. <https://doi.org/10.46627/silet.v5i3.528>
- Sánchez, J., Reyes-Rojas, J., & Alé-Silva, J. (2024). What is known about assistive technologies in distance and digital education for learners with disabilities? *Education Sciences*, 14(6), 595. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci14060595>
- Schauer, S., Simbeck, K., & Schüßler, L. (2025). Generating accessibility: Using AI to improve higher education for the visually impaired. *Proceedings of the 17th International Conference on Computer Supported Education*, 15-25. <https://doi.org/10.5220/0013136300003932>
- United Nations (2006). *Human Rights, convention on the rights of persons with impairment*. Retrieved from <https://www.ohchr.org> (Accessed July 7, 2025).